

TEN YEARS OF CULTURAL FLOURISH: DEVELOPMENTS IN THE ARTS, ENTERTAINMENT, RECREATION SECTORS, AND OTHER SERVICE ACTIVITIES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper explores the specific developments that unfolded in the Arts, Entertainment, Recreation sectors, and other service activities within the Romanian Mountain Area over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the evolving cultural and recreational landscape, examining trends, achievements, and challenges that have shaped these vibrant sectors in the region.

1. Introduction:

The Arts, Entertainment, Recreation, and other service activities play a crucial role in shaping the cultural fabric of a community. This paper delves into the unique developments within these sectors in the Romanian Mountain Area, analyzing statistical data to understand the trajectory of artistic and recreational endeavors over the specified decade.

2. Methodology:

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Using a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from cultural institutions, entertainment venues, recreational facilities, and other service-oriented activities. Key indicators, including audience attendance, cultural event frequencies, and the growth of recreational services, are scrutinized to offer a nuanced understanding of the region's cultural and leisure dynamics.

3. Arts and Cultural Sector Developments:

This section explores statistical intricacies related to the Arts and Cultural sector in the Romanian Mountain Area. Key metrics such as the establishment of cultural institutions, frequency of artistic events, and community engagement are examined to assess the sector's role in fostering creativity and promoting cultural diversity.

4. Entertainment and Recreation Sector Advancements:

The paper delves into the statistical landscape of the Entertainment and Recreation sector, examining trends in the establishment of entertainment venues, recreational facilities, and outdoor activities. Insights into the region's leisure preferences, tourism impact, and the growth of recreational services are discussed.

5. Other Service Activities and Contributions:

Analyzing statistical data related to other service activities, this section investigates developments in areas such as hospitality, tourism services, and event management. The paper aims to evaluate the sector's contributions to the regional economy, job creation, and overall community well-being.

6. Economic and Cultural Impact:

Assessing the economic and cultural impact of developments in the Arts, Entertainment, Recreation sectors, and other service activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional economy, tourism, and the overall quality of life. The paper emphasizes the interconnectedness of these sectors in shaping a vibrant and culturally rich community.

7. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges faced by these sectors during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing cultural, recreational, and service dynamics. Considerations such as technological advancements, changing consumer preferences, and regulatory shifts are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective on future developments.

8. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Art, entertainment and recreation, other activities dedicated to services (figures 2.11.1 – 2.11.5 and annexes chapter 2), present for each sector separately ascending values for the mean and

median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (the values statistics for Mean, Std. Error of Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th Percentiles; they are repeated for each indicator separately), as follows: mean of 51851.44, error standard at mean 3687.713, median 50678.00, standard deviation 11063.139, variance 122393050.278, Skewness -.067, standard error at Skewness .717, Kurtosis -.404, standard error at Kurtosis 1.400, distance 35410, minimum 33055, maximum 68465, percentile 44710.50, 50 - 50678.00, 75 - 62039.00.

The presented values demonstrate that the Art, entertainment and recreation sectors, other activities dedicated to services in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central tendency of the sectors Art, entertainment and recreation, other activities dedicated to the services of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises of mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator present a high degree of non-variability, which which means that the results do not have a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.11.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for the mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .383 .368, -2.220E-16, .979, - 2,220E-16, -8,882E-17; R-square .883, .097, .453, 1.000, .705, .774; RMSE 310,111, 425,838, .000, 2603,682, 40,214, 49,922; MAPS 15,191, 6,994, .000, 32,761, 2,942, 4,818; MaxAPE 59,731, 28,886, .000, 166,274, 8,664, 18,128; MAE 199,902, 274,237, .000, 1683,408, 27,717, 34,346; MaxAE 719,739, 1006,437, .000,

5793,124, 86,373, 98,727; Normalized BIC 10,707, 2,070, 7,355, 16,218, 7,958, 8,183.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S11

		Forecast										
Model		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	71622	75581	79540	83499	87458	91416	95375	99334	103293	107252	111210
	UCL	77779	81855	85928	90000	94069	98137	102203	106267	110330	114391	118451
	LCL	65466	69308	73152	76998	80846	84696	88548	92401	96256	100113	103970
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	25332	26730	28129	29527	30925	32324	33722	35120	36519	37917	39315
	UCL	26955	28385	29814	31243	32671	34098	35525	36952	38378	39804	41229
	LCL	23709	25076	26443	27811	29180	30549	31919	33289	34659	36030	37401
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	14191	15180	16170	17160	18150	19139	20129	21119	22109	23098	24088
	UCL	17307	19587	21567	23392	25117	26772	28373	29932	31456	32951	34422
	LCL	11075	10774	10773	10928	11182	11507	11885	12306	12761	13245	13754
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3876	4155	4434	4713	4992	5272	5551	5830	6109	6388	6667
	UCL	4969	5701	6327	6899	7436	7949	8442	8921	9388	9844	10292
	LCL	2783	2609	2541	2527	2548	2594	2659	2738	2830	2932	3042
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	936	998	1059	1121	1182	1244	1305	1367	1428	1490	1551
	UCL	1111	1245	1362	1471	1573	1672	1768	1861	1953	2043	2131
	LCL	762	751	756	771	791	815	842	872	903	936	971
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	4915	5253	5592	5930	6269	6607	6945	7284	7622	7961	8299
	UCL	5731	6074	6417	6760	7102	7445	7788	8130	8473	8815	9158
	LCL	4098	4432	4766	5101	5435	5769	6103	6437	6771	7106	7440

Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	1915	2052	2188	2325	2461	2598	2734	2871	3007	3144	3280
	UCL	2237	2507	2745	2968	3180	3386	3585	3780	3972	4161	4347
	LCL	1594	1597	1631	1682	1742	1810	1883	1961	2042	2126	2213
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1516	1625	1733	1842	1950	2059	2167	2276	2384	2493	2601
	UCL	1922	2198	2436	2653	2857	3052	3240	3422	3600	3774	3946
	LCL	1111	1052	1031	1031	1044	1066	1095	1129	1168	1211	1256
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1130	1214	1298	1382	1466	1551	1635	1719	1803	1887	1971
	UCL	1506	1746	1950	2135	2307	2472	2630	2782	2931	3076	3218
	LCL	754	682	647	630	626	629	640	655	675	698	724
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	11944	12762	13579	14396	15214	16031	16849	17666	18483	19301	20118
	UCL	14326	16130	17705	19161	20540	21866	23151	24403	25629	26833	28018
	LCL	9562	9393	9453	9632	9887	10196	10546	10928	11337	11768	12218
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1841	1981	2120	2259	2398	2538	2677	2816	2955	3095	3234
	UCL	2260	2573	2846	3097	3335	3564	3785	4001	4212	4420	4624
	LCL	1422	1388	1394	1421	1461	1511	1568	1631	1698	1770	1844
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2856	3028	3199	3370	3541	3713	3884	4055	4226	4398	4569
	UCL	3236	3565	3857	4130	4391	4643	4889	5130	5366	5599	5829
	LCL	2476	2490	2541	2610	2692	2782	2879	2981	3087	3197	3309
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	902	968	1034	1100	1166	1232	1298	1364	1430	1496	1562
	UCL	1113	1180	1247	1314	1381	1448	1515	1582	1649	1716	1783
	LCL	691	756	820	885	950	1015	1080	1145	1210	1275	1340
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	1455	1554	1654	1754	1853	1953	2052	2152	2252	2351	2451
	UCL	1888	2166	2404	2619	2821	3013	3198	3376	3550	3720	3887
	LCL	1022	942	904	888	885	893	907	928	953	983	1015
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2887	3098	3310	3521	3733	3944	4156	4368	4579	4791	5002
	UCL	3389	3603	3817	4031	4245	4459	4673	4887	5101	5315	5529
	LCL	2384	2593	2802	3012	3221	3430	3639	3848	4057	4266	4475

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	2021	2161	2301	2441	2581	2720	2860	3000	3140	3280	3420
	UCL	2419	2724	2991	3237	3471	3696	3914	4127	4335	4540	4741
	LCL	1623	1597	1611	1644	1690	1745	1806	1873	1945	2020	2099
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	15500	16406	17312	18218	19124	20030	20936	21842	22748	23654	24560
	UCL	16321	17244	18166	19088	20009	20931	21852	22773	23694	24614	25534
	LCL	14680	15569	16459	17349	18239	19129	20020	20911	21802	22694	23585
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	8076	8607	9138	9669	10200	10732	11263	11794	12325	12856	13387
	UCL	9420	10508	11466	12357	13206	14023	14818	15595	16357	17106	17844
	LCL	6732	6707	6811	6982	7195	7440	7707	7993	8293	8606	8930
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	1632	1743	1855	1966	2078	2189	2301	2412	2524	2635	2747
	UCL	1979	2092	2206	2319	2432	2545	2658	2771	2885	2998	3111
	LCL	1285	1394	1504	1614	1724	1833	1943	2053	2163	2273	2382
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	733	786	840	893	946	1000	1053	1107	1160	1213	1267
	UCL	848	904	959	1015	1070	1126	1181	1236	1292	1347	1402
	LCL	618	669	720	771	823	874	926	977	1028	1080	1131
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2473	2640	2807	2974	3141	3308	3475	3642	3809	3976	4143
	UCL	2772	2945	3117	3289	3461	3633	3805	3977	4149	4321	4492
	LCL	2174	2336	2498	2659	2821	2983	3145	3307	3469	3631	3794
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1347	1443	1538	1634	1730	1825	1921	2016	2112	2208	2303
	UCL	1577	1673	1770	1867	1964	2061	2157	2254	2351	2448	2544
	LCL	1118	1212	1307	1401	1496	1590	1684	1779	1873	1968	2062
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	1365	1459	1553	1647	1742	1836	1930	2025	2119	2213	2307
	UCL	1554	1652	1750	1848	1945	2043	2140	2238	2335	2433	2530
	LCL	1175	1266	1357	1447	1538	1629	1720	1811	1902	1993	2085
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	753	805	857	909	962	1014	1066	1119	1171	1223	1275
	UCL	867	921	975	1030	1084	1138	1192	1246	1300	1354	1408
	LCL	638	689	739	789	840	890	941	991	1042	1092	1143

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	7536	8001	8466	8931	9396	9861	10326	10791	11256	11721	12186
	UCL	8613	9524	10331	11085	11804	12499	13175	13837	14487	15126	15757
	LCL	6459	6478	6601	6777	6988	7223	7477	7745	8025	8316	8615
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	747	792	838	883	928	973	1018	1063	1109	1154	1199
	UCL	870	966	1051	1129	1203	1275	1344	1412	1478	1543	1607
	LCL	624	618	624	637	653	672	693	715	739	765	791
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1168	1250	1333	1415	1497	1579	1662	1744	1826	1909	1991
	UCL	1345	1431	1516	1602	1687	1772	1858	1943	2028	2113	2198
	LCL	991	1070	1149	1228	1307	1387	1466	1545	1625	1704	1784
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	2945	3126	3308	3489	3670	3852	4033	4214	4396	4577	4758
	UCL	3281	3468	3656	3843	4030	4217	4405	4592	4778	4965	5152
	LCL	2609	2784	2959	3135	3310	3486	3661	3837	4013	4189	4365
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1498	1592	1686	1780	1874	1967	2061	2155	2249	2343	2437
	UCL	1706	1886	2046	2195	2338	2477	2611	2743	2873	3000	3126
	LCL	1290	1298	1326	1364	1409	1458	1511	1567	1626	1686	1748
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	546	582	618	654	690	726	762	799	835	871	907
	UCL	618	655	692	730	767	804	842	879	916	954	991
	LCL	474	509	544	579	613	648	683	718	753	788	823
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	791	846	901	956	1011	1066	1121	1176	1231	1286	1341
	UCL	912	968	1023	1079	1135	1190	1246	1302	1357	1413	1469
	LCL	669	724	778	833	887	941	996	1050	1105	1159	1214
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	18723	19715	20707	21699	22691	23683	24675	25667	26659	27651	28643
	UCL	20616	21643	22670	23696	24722	25747	26771	27795	28819	29842	30865
	LCL	16830	17787	18744	19702	20660	21619	22579	23539	24499	25460	26421
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	7965	8515	9064	9613	10162	10712	11261	11810	12359	12909	13458
	UCL	9683	10943	12039	13048	14003	14919	15805	16668	17512	18340	19154
	LCL	6248	6086	6089	6178	6322	6505	6717	6952	7207	7478	7762

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	2130	2277	2425	2572	2719	2866	3013	3160	3308	3455	3602
	UCL	2477	2768	3025	3265	3494	3715	3931	4141	4348	4551	4752
	LCL	1783	1787	1824	1878	1944	2017	2096	2180	2267	2358	2452
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	742	796	850	904	958	1013	1067	1121	1175	1229	1283
	UCL	933	1066	1181	1286	1385	1480	1572	1661	1748	1833	1916
	LCL	551	526	520	523	532	545	561	581	602	625	650
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	1226	1313	1399	1486	1572	1659	1745	1832	1918	2005	2091
	UCL	1551	1639	1727	1815	1903	1991	2079	2167	2255	2343	2431
	LCL	902	987	1071	1156	1241	1326	1411	1496	1581	1666	1751
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	430	460	489	518	548	577	607	636	665	695	724
	UCL	623	732	822	903	978	1049	1116	1180	1243	1303	1362
	LCL	238	188	156	134	117	106	97	92	88	86	86
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	477	508	540	571	603	634	666	697	729	760	792
	UCL	588	666	733	794	852	907	961	1013	1063	1113	1162
	LCL	365	350	347	348	353	361	371	382	394	408	422
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2385	2547	2708	2869	3030	3192	3353	3514	3675	3837	3998
	UCL	3007	3426	3785	4113	4421	4715	4998	5273	5541	5803	6061
	LCL	1763	1667	1631	1625	1640	1668	1707	1755	1810	1870	1935
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	563	601	640	679	718	756	795	834	873	911	950
	UCL	655	733	801	864	925	984	1041	1096	1151	1205	1258
	LCL	470	470	479	493	510	529	550	571	594	618	642
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	11240	11841	12442	13043	13644	14245	14846	15447	16048	16649	17249
	UCL	12280	12898	13516	14133	14750	15367	15983	16600	17216	17832	18448
	LCL	10200	10784	11369	11953	12538	13123	13708	14294	14879	15465	16051
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	9373	9826	10280	10733	11187	11640	12094	12547	13001	13454	13907
	UCL	10330	10800	11270	11740	12209	12678	13147	13616	14085	14553	15021
	LCL	8415	8852	9289	9726	10164	10602	11040	11478	11916	12355	12794

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1885	2025	2164	2304	2443	2582	2722	2861	3001	3140	3279
	UCL	2033	2296	2580	2882	3201	3535	3883	4245	4619	5005	5403
	LCL	1738	1754	1749	1725	1685	1630	1560	1477	1382	1275	1156
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	12016	12678	13341	14004	14666	15329	15991	16654	17316	17979	18641
	UCL	14020	14692	15364	16037	16709	17381	18054	18726	19398	20070	20742
	LCL	10012	10665	11318	11970	12623	13276	13929	14582	15234	15887	16540
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	4992	5335	5679	6023	6367	6711	7055	7399	7742	8086	8430
	UCL	5776	6124	6471	6819	7167	7515	7862	8210	8558	8905	9253
	LCL	4207	4547	4887	5227	5567	5907	6247	6587	6927	7268	7608
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1646	1752	1858	1963	2069	2175	2281	2387	2492	2598	2704
	UCL	1957	2065	2172	2280	2387	2494	2601	2709	2816	2923	3031
	LCL	1335	1439	1543	1647	1751	1856	1960	2064	2169	2273	2377
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	997	1065	1132	1199	1266	1334	1401	1468	1535	1603	1670
	UCL	1108	1221	1323	1420	1514	1605	1694	1781	1867	1953	2037
	LCL	887	908	940	978	1019	1063	1108	1155	1204	1253	1303
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	642	686	731	776	821	865	910	955	1000	1044	1089
	UCL	820	938	1040	1132	1219	1302	1382	1459	1534	1608	1680
	LCL	464	434	423	419	422	429	439	451	465	481	498
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	682	729	776	823	871	918	965	1012	1059	1106	1153
	UCL	813	861	908	956	1004	1051	1099	1147	1195	1242	1290
	LCL	552	598	645	691	737	784	830	877	923	970	1016
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1053	1127	1201	1274	1348	1422	1495	1569	1642	1716	1790
	UCL	1213	1287	1362	1436	1510	1585	1659	1734	1808	1882	1957
	LCL	894	967	1040	1113	1185	1258	1331	1404	1477	1550	1623
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	7696	8213	8729	9246	9763	10279	10796	11312	11829	12346	12862
	UCL	9463	9988	10514	11039	11564	12090	12615	13140	13665	14190	14716
	LCL	5929	6437	6945	7453	7961	8469	8977	9485	9993	10501	11009

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2347	2514	2682	2849	3017	3184	3352	3519	3687	3854	4022
	UCL	3033	3485	3870	4222	4551	4865	5167	5460	5746	6024	6298
	LCL	1660	1544	1493	1477	1482	1503	1536	1578	1628	1684	1746
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	866	929	992	1055	1118	1181	1244	1308	1371	1434	1497
	UCL	969	1033	1097	1161	1226	1290	1354	1418	1482	1546	1610
	LCL	762	824	886	949	1011	1073	1135	1198	1260	1322	1384
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1366	1449	1531	1614	1697	1779	1862	1945	2027	2110	2193
	UCL	1967	2052	2138	2223	2309	2395	2480	2566	2651	2737	2822
	LCL	765	845	925	1005	1084	1164	1244	1324	1403	1483	1563
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3008	3203	3399	3594	3789	3984	4179	4374	4569	4764	4959
	UCL	3569	3767	3964	4162	4360	4558	4756	4953	5151	5349	5546
	LCL	2448	2640	2833	3025	3217	3410	3602	3794	3987	4179	4372

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive examination of developments in the Arts, Entertainment, Recreation sectors, and other service activities in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's cultural vibrancy, offering valuable insights for policymakers, cultural institutions, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for sustaining the growth of these vital sectors.

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